

THE PROBLEMS OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

English has been designated as a source of intercultural communication among the people from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds. The article suggests the utilization of communicative strategies that specialize in the event of learners' efficiency in communicating language through cultural context¹. Therefore, the assignment study recommends integration of cultural awareness into a teaching programme for an overall achievement of competence in intercultural communication.

Keywords: *english teaching, international culture, cultural awareness, intercultural communication, world languages, context, language tool.*

INTRODUCTION

With today's increasing globalization of social and economic activities, people's understanding of English learning has been further enhanced. Today, people's understanding of the language is no longer limited to the narrow concept

¹<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-importance-of-intercultural-communication-in-foreign-language-learning>

“communication tool”. Language is an inseparable part of culture; it is the carrier of culture. Language reflects the characteristics of a nation; it contains not only the nation’s historical and cultural background, but also the nation’s views on life, life style and mode of thinking. To learn a foreign language, you have to master the knowledge, skills and also have to understand the language which reflected the foreign culture, so as to overcome cultural barriers, communicate with foreigners decently and effectively and have emotional communication and cross-cultural communication¹.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY.

Intercultural communication is a discipline that studies communication across different cultures and social groups, or how culture affects communication. It describes the wide range of communication processes and problems that naturally appear within an organization or social context made up of individuals from different religious, social, ethnic, and educational backgrounds. In this sense, it seeks to understand how people from different countries and cultures act, communicate, and perceive the world around them. Intercultural communication focuses on the recognition and respect of those with cultural differences. The goal is mutual adaptation between two or more distinct cultures which leads to biculturalism/multiculturalism rather than complete assimilation. It promotes the development of cultural sensitivity and allows for empathic understanding across different cultures².

According to a study published in the Washington post based on a 15-year research of the University of Dusseldorf, in 2015 English was among the most widely spread languages in the world as a native language, with bilingual speakers also included in the data search (Noack & Gamio, 2015). Table 1 presents statistics of the languages with the largest number of native speakers³:

¹ <https://www.atlantis-press.com/article/12635.pdf>

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Intercultural_communication

³ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/361568479_The_role_of_English_in_intercultural_communication_Past_modernity_and_future_global_perspectives/link/62bd00b9f9dee438e8cd0be3/download?_tp=eyJjb250ZXh0Ijp7ImZpcnN0UGFnZSI6InB1YmxpY2F0aW9uIiwicGFnZSI6InB1YmxpY2F0aW9uIn19

Table 1
Native speakers of the world's top ten most widespread languages

NO.	LANGUAGE	NUMBER OF NATIVE SPEAKERS
1.	Chinese	1.39 bln
2.	Hindu-Urdu	588 mln
3.	English	527 mln
4.	Arabic	467 mln
5.	Spanish	389 mln
6.	Russian	254 mln
7.	Bengali	250 mln
8.	Portuguese	193 mln
9.	German	132 mln
10.	Japanese	123 mln

In foreign language teaching, the necessity of language and culture teaching has become the consensus of the people, because the cultivation of communicative competence includes two aspects: Mastering the language rules and the rules of language use, namely, linguistic competence and pragmatic competence. Here language ability refers to the pronunciation, vocabulary and grammar part, namely English in listening, speaking, reading, writing and translating, the five basic skills of language use, here refers to the language used is appropriate cultural factors and rules. Language and culture are closely linked, some background knowledge of language and culture is helpful to promote the language application ability, three elements of language syllabus (pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary) teaching already had the quite perfect system, but for the intercultural teaching it should include what elements are not clear. Following from teaching and learning perspective and cognitive perspective, we talk about how to cultivate the consciousness and ability of intercultural communication.

The issue of the lack of publications, may it be books, textbooks, articles or anything else, becomes undeniable if one looks at online databases or shops. The analysis of such sources has shown that the dominance of English as the language of intercultural studies is uncontested. Table 1 reflects the current situation with books on intercultural communication; the figures are given as a result of search through these websites based on the key words 'intercultural communication' and the language criterion. The number of books available in English is much higher than for other languages.

The importance of creating textbooks of high quality is undeniable, and when it comes to textbooks on intercultural communication authors should understand how to choose the right approach to writing them. Safonova in her paper on intercultural communication educational materials outlines five methodological principles of such work¹:

- 1) correlation between global and national,
- 2) priority of intercultural dominant idea,
- 3) creation of problem-oriented methodological environment,
- 4) orientation towards professionally relevant bilingualism,
- 5) a multiple-level system.

A language acquires value and meaning only when it is integrated with the cultural elements as language is a part of culture and culture is a part of language. Culture and language are used and considered as a unit. Only when there is cultural awareness then only critical thinking comes in as mere information is not useful and it becomes meaningless. Therefore to understand a language first it is essential to have not only knowledge of grammar, phonology and lexis but also certain features and characteristics of the culture. Each culture has its own cultural values and aspects and these values change from one culture to another. Oetzel (2008) believes that cultural differences produce difference in communication style that can vary across

¹ https://www.shs-conferences.org/articles/shsconf/pdf/2021/36/shsconf_tlm2021_01001.pdf

cultures and can lead to misunderstandings and misinterpretation. These misunderstandings can also occur due to expectations of communication in a certain culture which is not fulfilled by the counter party. Sometimes the values might be completely different. So it leads to communicating problems among speakers and learners who are not aware of the values and features of other culture. Globalization in various fields like markets, technical advancements, intercultural workforce, international tourism and immigration has made the world a global village. To understand the people and culture of another village it is essential to be equipped with the right words. The right cross cultural communication gives an individual the best opportunities to share ideas, experiences and perceptions by interaction. The important criteria for successful communication is to avoid using slang and idioms for a successful communication. Words conveying only specific meaning must be chosen. It is better to listen carefully before starting to communicate. Local accents and pronunciation become a problem and an obstacle for effective communication. So if there is a doubt and it is difficult to understand the other person it is better for confirmation of understanding¹.

CONCLUSION.

Culture being a crucial and integral a part of human society deals with the communication of language by the individuals during a sort of situations and circumstances. An outsized number of scholars and professionals from Uzbekistan tend to find out English as a far off Language (EFL) for the satisfaction of communicative and practical purposes of life. Language and culture are closely interrelated, and English now holds a leading role in intercultural communication around the world with the largest number of learners who choose to learn English for successful social adaptation and to develop intercultural awareness The dominance of English is due to linguistic and extralinguistic factors, a combination of which has

¹ <https://www.internationaljournalssrg.org/IJHSS/2018/Volume5-Issue4/IJHSS-V5I4P104.pdf>

made English a modern lingua franca. Linguistic factors lie in its grammatical simplicity and rich vocabulary. English is a dominant language in various spheres, including politics, media, science, the economy, education, and recreation, which is why both businesses and individuals choose to learn and use English to achieve a high standard of intercultural communication.

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